

Efficiency Evaluation of Some Plant Extracts and ZnONPs on the Bacteria *Klebsiella pneumoniae* that Causes Rot Onion in Storage

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Abstract:

This study was conducted at the laboratories of the College of Agriculture/Plant Protection Department at the University of Kufa according to a completely randomized design (CRD) to determine the extent of the effect of the alcoholic extract (*Cinnamomum zeylanicum*, *Cissus rhombifolia*) and ZnONPs at concentrations 10, 20 and 30% for each plant on the genus of bacteria *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. The results showed that the alcoholic extracts and ZnONPs gave a high efficiency in inhibiting bacteria for the studied traits minimum inhibitory concentration test 30% concentration of the alcoholic cinnamon extract and ZnONPs of the study gave a high inhibitory

ability compared to the rest of the concentrations, as it was found that the inhibitory ability of the extract, increases with increasing concentration.

Keywords: *Cinnamomum zeylanicum*, *Cissus rhombifolia*, ZnONPs.

Introduction

Onion (*Allium cepa* L.) is a common vegetable belonging to the Alliaceae family. Onions are consumed fresh and dried in Iraq all over the world. In addition to its pungent properties, phytonutrients and antioxidants (Liguori et al., 2017). At present, many medicinal plants have been used. Their seeds, flowers, leaves, and roots, as well as some buds and stems, have many active substances that are effective against pathogenic and productive microorganisms. They are secondary metabolic compounds that are effective against plant pathogens and others. The history of the use of plant extracts and powders goes back to the time The ancient Egyptians and Greeks (Duke, 1990; Gerhard and

Rudolf, 2005; Saratha and Subramanian, 2010). In order to reduce pollution and control the occurrence of any side effects harmful to health and the environment, this is done through the use of plant extracts, as several studies have proven that plants contain a number of effective compounds that have antimicrobial activity. Most antimicrobial activity appears to be associated with phenolic compounds and the antimicrobial effect is mainly related to changes in the permeability and integrity of the bacterial cell membrane (Lambert et al., 2001). Studies have shown the mechanism of the effect of cinnamon extract on bacteria, by damaging the cell membrane and inhibiting ATPase, as well as on bacterial cell division and movement, as it contains cinnamic acid, which affects both gram-

negative and gram-positive bacteria, as well as synergistic interactions with anti-bacterials approved in treatments as well. It has an effect on the cytoplasm and cell membrane, which changes the cell morphology (the apparent appearance) of bacterial cells, because it contains the substance methoxy cinnamaldehyde (Vasconcelos et al., 2018). A study was also conducted in the laboratory using 28 plant extracts, oils, and some antibiotics with a concentration of 5% against gram-negative bacteria. It was reported that among the materials that showed positive results was Al-Mariri extract (Al-Mariri et al., 2014). Cinnamon oil has antibacterial activity against Gram-positive and Gram-negative strains (Mohammad et al., 2022). Studies have shown that sage has antimicrobial activity against some microorganisms and that when used with antibiotics, it has favorable potential against multi-resistant bacteria (Voukeng et al., 2012). Also, grape leaf extract's antioxidant activity can result from the synergistic action of various classes of bioactive compounds (Gülcü et al., 2020, Liang et al., 2021). Recent studies revealed that levels of polyphenols in grape leaves are in quantities similar to those found in grapes and grape seeds with antimicrobials (Ramadan et al., 2017). As nanoparticles can be applied directly to plant seeds, leaves, and even roots to protect against pests and pathogens, one study has shown that nanosized zinc oxide has antifungal and antibacterial properties (Worrall et al., 2018).

Materials and Methods

Preparation of the Alcoholic Extract of *Cinnamomum zeylanicum*

A quantity of cinnamon sticks was obtained from local markets, then ground, then 20 gm of cinnamon powder was taken and placed in an electric blender with 400 ml of 95% ethyl alcohol and mixed several times to obtain a homogeneous mixture (Harborne, 1984). After that the mixture was filtered using sterile filter paper and then passed through a Millipore. Whatman 0.20 μ m to get rid of impurities and bacteria, then put the filtrate in the oven at a

temperature of 45°C to evaporate the alcohol. A stock 100% fully effective compound was considered for the alcoholic extract of cinnamon and it was stored in airtight glass bottles in the refrigerator at 4°C until use.

Preparation of Alcoholic Extract of *Cissus rhombifolia* Grape Leaves

A quantity of fresh grape leaves was collected. After that, the leaves were washed well with sterile distilled water several times to remove any dust and dirt related to them. They were then placed on filter papers to remove excess water. They were then dried in indirect sunlight, and after they were completely dry, they were ground. Take 20 g of the powder and put it in an electric blender with 400 ml of ethyl alcohol at a concentration of 95% and mix it several times to obtain a homogeneous mixture (Harborne, 1984). After that, the mixture was filtered using sterile filter paper and then passed through a Millipore. Whatman 0.20 μ m to get rid of impurities and then put the filtrate in the oven at a temperature of 45°C to evaporate the alcohol. It was considered a fully effective stock 100% compound for the alcoholic extract of grape leaves and it was stored in airtight glass bottles in the refrigerator at 4°C until use.

Preparation of Zinc Oxide Nano Materials (ZnONPs)

Dissolve the prepared zinc oxide nanoparticles using an ultrasonic device for two minutes with 10 ml of 95% ethyl alcohol and use it in all subsequent experiments (Sarvamangala et al., 2013).

Preparation of Nutrient Agar N.A Medium

It was prepared by dissolving 29 g of the ready-made nutrient medium in a liter of distilled water, according to the instructions of the medium manufacturer (Hi-Media, India), taking into account not adding antibiotics to ensure the growth of bacteria on it. It was mixed well, after which it was distributed into tightly sealed glass flasks of capacity. 250 ml and sterilized in an autoclave for 20 minutes and at a pressure of 121 pounds/inch². After the end of the sterilization period, it was stored in the refrigerator until use.

Preparation Nutrient Broth N.B Medium

It was prepared by adding 13 g of the prepared medium to 1 liter of distilled water, according to the instructions of the medium manufacturer (Hi-Media, India), and was mixed well. After that, it was distributed into sealed glass flasks with a capacity of 250 ml and sterilized in the autoclave for 20 minutes, at a pressure of 15. After the end of the sterilization period, it was left to cool and then stored in the refrigerator until use.

Minimum Inhibition Concentration (MIC) Test of Alcoholic Grape Leaves Extract on the Growth of *Klebsiella pneumonia* Bacteria Using a Filter Disk

The lowest inhibitory concentration of alcoholic grape leaf extract was tested on the bacteria *Klebsiella pneumonia*, according to the method used by Jorgensen et al. (2015). 50 microliters of the bacterial suspension at a concentration of 10^7 was spread on Nutrient Agar using sterile cotton swab. Equal filter discs sterilized by autoclaving and saturated with different concentrations of alcoholic extract at concentrations of 10, 20, and 30% were taken separately and placed in the dish containing the solid medium, as each dish contains a different concentration with 6 replicates of each concentration with a water control treatment. The plates were only incubated at a temperature of 30°C for 48 hours, after which the inhibition zone was measured using the measurement units marked in millimeters, and the inhibitory concentration was considered the lowest inhibitory concentration for the bacteria.

Minimum Inhibition Concentration (MIC) Test of Alcoholic Cinnamon Extract on the Growth of *Klebsiella pneumonia* Using a Filter Disk

The lowest inhibitory concentration of the alcoholic cinnamon extract of the students was tested on the bacteria *Klebsiella pneumonia*, according to the method used by Jorgensen et al. (2015). 50 microliters of the bacterial suspension at a concentration of 10^7 was spread on the solid medium, Nutrient Agar, using sterile cotton swab swabs. Equal filter discs sterilized by

autoclaving, which were saturated with different concentrations of the extract at concentrations of 10-20-30%, were taken individually and placed in the dish containing the solid medium, as each dish contained a different concentration with three replicates of each concentration with a control treatment of water only, and the dishes were incubated. At a temperature of 30 degrees Celsius for 48 hours, after which the inhibition zone was measured using the units of measurement in millimeters, and the inhibitory concentration was considered the lowest inhibitory concentration for the bacteria.

Minimum Inhibition Concentration (MIC) Test for Alcoholic Cinnamon Extract and Alcoholic Grape Leaf Extract Against the Bacteria *Klebsiella pneumonia*

This test was conducted to determine the minimum inhibitory concentration of the alcoholic extract of cinnamon and the alcoholic grape leaf extract against the bacteria *Klebsiella pneumonia* according to the method used by (Ahmed et al., 2017). Concentrations of 10-20-30% for each treatment/liter of Nutrient Broth were prepared as the final concentration in glass test tubes. The tubes were inoculated individually with a bacterial suspension of 100 micro litres (10^7 colony-forming units/ml of water) and incubated at 30°C for 48 hours. Then, 1 ml was taken from each tube and placed in an empty petri dish, and sterilized and cooled Nutrient Agar was added to it before solidifying, while stirring the dishes in a constant motion. Lightly for the purpose of homogeneity, the dishes were incubated at a temperature of 30 degrees Celsius for 48 hours, and then the number of growing bacterial colonies in each dish was calculated. The failure of any colony to grow in the dish was considered the inhibitory concentration of the tested substance. The experiment was conducted with 3 replicates for each treatment and a control treatment for each treatment.

Statistical Analysis

The experiment was RCD with three replications. Data were analyzed and analysis of variance ANOVA and means were compared

according to Least significant difference LSD ($P \leq 0.05$) using GenStat software.

Results and Discussion

Minimum Inhibition Concentration (MIC) of Alcoholic Grape Leaf Extract on the Growth of *Klebsiella pneumonia* Bacteria Using a Filter Disk in N.A Medium at 30°C

The results showed by determining the antibacterial activity using alcoholic grape leaf extract against the *K. pneumonia* bacteria, where significant differences were also found, as the results showed with different concentrations against the *K. pneumonia* bacteria, that the concentration of 30 and 20 ml had a clear percentage of inhibiting the bacteria, reaching 0.7, 0.9 Respectively compared to the control treatment, which amounted to 0.00 mm.

Table 1. The Inhibitory Ability of Concentrations of Alcoholic Grape Leaf Extract and the Pathogenic Bacteria *Klebsiella pneumonia* in N.A Medium at 30°C

Inhibition distance (mm)	Concentrations%
6	10
7	20
9	30
0.00	Control
3.261	LSD = 0.05

Minimum Inhibition Concentration (MIC) of Alcoholic Cinnamon Extract on the Growth of *Klebsiella pneumonia* Bacteria Using a Filter Disk in N.A Medium at 30°C

The results showed by determining the antibacterial activity using the alcoholic cinnamon extract of the students against the bacteria *K. pneumonia*, where significant differences were found, as the results showed with different concentrations against the bacteria *K. pneumonia*, that the concentration of 30 and 20 ml had a clear percentage of inhibiting the bacteria, reaching 10.16, 10.36 respectively. Compared to the control treatment, which amounted to 0.00 mm.

Table 2. The Inhibitory Ability of Concentrations of Alcoholic Cinnamon Extract and Pathogenic Bacteria *Klebsiella pneumonia* that Causes Onion Rot in N.A Medium at 30°C

Inhibition distance (mm)	Concentrations%
8	10
10.16	20
10.36	30
0.00	Control
2.669	LSD = 0.05

Minimum Inhibition Concentration (MIC) ZnONPs on the Growth of *Klebsiella pneumonia* Bacteria Using a Filter Disk in N.A Medium at 30°C

The results showed by determining the antibacterial activity using ZnONPs against the *K. pneumonia* bacteria, where significant differences were found. The results showed with the different concentrations against the *K. pneumonia* bacteria, that all concentrations led to the inhibition of the bacteria and increased with increasing concentration for each of the concentrations 10, 20 And 30% ml, which amounted to (9.0, 11.93, 13.5), respectively, compared to the control treatment, which amounted to (0.00 ml).

Table 3. The Inhibitory Ability of Concentrations ZnONPs on Bacteria *Klebsiella pneumonia* that Causes Onion Rot in N.A Medium at 30°C

Inhibition distance (mm)	Concentrations%
9	10
11.93	20
13.5	30
0.00	Control
3.261	LSD = 0.05

Minimum Inhibition Concentration (MIC) for Alcoholic Cinnamon Extract and Alcoholic Grape Leaf Extract against the Bacteria *Klebsiella pneumonia* N.A Medium at 30°C

The results of the minimum inhibitory concentration of alcoholic cinnamon extract, alcoholic grape leaf extract and ZnONPs against

the bacteria *Klebsiella pneumonia* showed a decrease in the number of bacterial colonies growing on the Neutron Agar medium with increasing concentrations. The number of bacterial colonies at the concentration 30% of alcoholic cinnamon extract reached 0.00 colonies at pH levels of 7.0 and 7.5. No colony survived in the dish compared to the control treatment, which amounted to $10^7 \times 17.54$ colonies/ml after 48 hours of incubating the dishes at 30 degrees Celsius, as shown in the table (4). The number of bacterial colonies at 30% concentration of alcoholic grape leaf extract reached 0.25 colonies at pH 7.0 and 7.5 compared to the control treatment, which amounted to $10^7 \times 15.63$ colonies/ml after 48 hours of incubating the dishes at 30 degrees

Celsius. The number of bacterial colonies at the concentration of 30% for ZnONPs reached (0.00) colonies at the pH level of 7.0 and 7.5 compared to the control treatment, which amounted to $10^7 \times 18.46$ colonies / ml after 48 hours of incubating the dishes at 30 degrees Celsius. The antibiotic process is one of the most important phenomena used in biological resistance, as it causes inhibition of the growth of the pathogen, eliminates it completely, or stops the germination of its reproductive units. This phenomenon depends on the ability of the biological agent to produce antibiotics, which are byproducts consisting of toxic substances that affect the pathogen. pathogenesis (Kohl et al., 2019).

Table 3. The Inhibitory Ability of Different Concentrations of Alcoholic Grape Leaf Extract, Alcoholic Cinnamon Extract, and Nano-Zinc Oxide (ZnONPs) in Counting the Number of Bacterial Colonies (C.f.u) that Causes Onion Rot in N.A Medium at 30°C.

Extract	concentration%	Average number of colonies x 10 ⁷
Cinnamon	10	1.18
	20	0.44
	30	0.0
	control	17.54
	L.S.D	1.883
Grape leaves	10	4.12
	20	1.92
	30	0.25
	control	15.63
	L.S.D	2.663
ZnONPs	10	1.12
	20	0.25
	30	0.00
	Control	18.46
	L.S.D	1.883

Figur4. The Inhibitory Ability of Different Concentrations of Alcoholic Grape Leaf Extract, Alcoholic Cinnamon Extract, and Nano-Zinc Oxide (ZnONPs) in Counting the Number of Bacterial Colonies (C.f.u.) that Causes Onion Rot in N.A Medium at 30°C

Conclusion

The alcoholic extracts (*C. zeylanicum* and *C. rhombifolia*) and ZnONPs showed high efficiency in inhibiting *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. The 30% concentration of alcoholic cinnamon extract and ZnONPs exhibited the highest inhibitory ability. Increasing the concentration of the extracts led to a higher inhibitory effect, indicating a concentration-dependent relationship. Plant extracts and ZnONPs have the potential to be effective agents against *Klebsiella pneumoniae* in storage facilities.

Future research could focus on practical applications of these extracts and ZnONPs in real storage conditions to assess their effectiveness in controlling bacterial growth. Natural products like plant extracts offer a promising alternative to traditional chemical-based antimicrobials for combating bacterial pathogens. The study emphasizes the antimicrobial properties of alcoholic plant extracts and ZnONPs, providing insights for future research on bacterial control in agriculture.

References

- Ahmed, F. A., Arif, M., & Alvarez, A. M. (2017). Antibacterial effect of potassium tetraborate tetrahydrate against soft rot disease agent *Pectobacterium carotovorum* in tomato. *Frontiers in microbiology*, 8, 1728. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2017.01728>
- Al-Mariri, A., & Safi, M. (2014). In vitro antibacterial activity of several plant extracts and oils against some gram-negative bacteria. *Iranian journal of medical sciences*, 39(1), 36.
- Duke, O.S. (1990). *Natural Pesticides From Plant*. Print in USA. pp. 511–517.
- Gerhard, A. and M. Rudolf. 2005. Engineered Ribosomal protein limits plant Resistance to mycotoxin. *Information Systems for Biotechnology*, 329-340. (Annual Newsletter). <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-7652.2004.00075.x>
- Harborne, J.B. (1984). *Phytochemical Method. A guide to Modern Techniques of plants Analysis*. 2nd Ed. Chapman and Hall. New York. USA. pp. 288.
- Jorgensen, J. H., & Turnidge, J. D. (2015). Susceptibility test methods: dilution and disk diffusion methods. *Manual of clinical microbiology*, 1253-1273. <https://doi.org/10.1128/9781555817381.ch71>
- Lambert, R. J. W., Skandamis, P. N., Coote, P. J., & Nychas, G. J. (2001). A study of the minimum inhibitory concentration and mode of action of oregano essential oil, thymol and carvacrol. *Journal of applied microbiology*, 91(3), 453-462. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2672.2001.01428.x>
- Liguori, L., Califano, R., Albanese, D., Raimo, F., Crescitelli, A., & Di Matteo, M. (2017). Chemical composition and antioxidant properties of five white onion (*Allium cepa* L.) landraces. *Journal of food quality*, 2017(1), 6873651. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2017%2F6873651>
- Saratha, V., & Subramanian, S.P. (2010). Evaluation of antifungal activity of *Calotropis gigantea* latex extract: an in vitro study. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research*, 1, 88-96.
- Voukeng, I. K., Kuete, V., Dzoyem, J. P., Fankam, A. G., Noumedem, J. A., Kuate, J. R., & Pages, J. M. (2012). Antibacterial and antibiotic-potential activities of the methanol extract of some cameroonian spices against Gram-negative multi-drug resistant phenotypes. *BMC Research Notes*, 5, 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1756-0500-5-299>
- Köhl, J., Kolnaar, R., & Ravensberg, W. J. (2019). Mode of action of microbial biological control agents against plant diseases: relevance beyond efficacy. *Frontiers in plant science*, 10, 454982. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2019.00845>
- Vasconcelos, N. G., Croda, J., & Simionatto, S. (2018). Antibacterial mechanisms of cinnamon and its constituents: A review. *Microbial*

